

"Women and Nutrition in this polarised world"

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Abstract:

My paper explores that the health and nutrition of women and girls is of particular concern because, in many societies, they are disadvantaged by discrimination rooted in sociocultural factors. Those are including heart disease, diabetes, stroke, some cancers, and osteoporosis, high blood pressure, high cholesterol etc... Women represent the cornerstone of a family's overall health, ensuring they have access to quality care also can lead to improved health for children and families. The health of families and communities are no doubt, tied to the health of women. So that nutritional food is very important to women for her well-being, ability to fight off illness, ability to recover from illness or injury. The diets of women in India are often too poor to meet their nutritional needs. It's essential to take steps to improve her well-being with nutrition.

Key words: Women Health, Nutrition, Food, wellness, polarised world etc.

Introduction:

Women represent the cornerstone of a family's overall health, ensuring they have access to quality care also can lead to improved health for children and families. The health of families and communities are no doubt, tied to the health of women. Women's health refers to the branch of medicine that focuses on the treatment and diagnosis of diseases and conditions that affect a woman's physical and emotional well-being. Well-nourished women are better able to provide for themselves, their children, and their families. Well-nourished mothers are more likely to have infants with healthy birth weights, and such children are less likely to ever suffer from malnutrition. A well-balanced diet, comprised of a variety of foods, adequately meets women's needs for vitamins, minerals and energy. For good health, women need to pay special attention to calcium, iron and folate (folic acid) intake. A healthy diet also should minimize the intake of fat and sugar.

Women and her nutritional life:

Balanced nutrition and a healthy diet can support woman body in many ways. Whether Woman is looking to improve her energy and mood, combat stress, or boost fertility, what her fuel to her body with can make an impact. To help explain how nutrition can impact on her is to studying. it's very important to acknowledge that men and women have differing nutritional needs as a result of differences in their bodies. For example, hormonal changes associated with menstruation, childbearing, and menopause mean that women have a higher risk of anemia, osteoporosis, and various nutritional deficiencies. For this reason, it's important for women to include foods rich in calcium, vitamin D, B vitamins, and iron in their diet to maintain bone health and prevent anemia. Women also tend to lose more lean muscle mass over time due to age and

childbearing. Therefore, a regular exercise regimen that includes weight training and/or high-intensity workouts should be a part of her routine. Regularly scheduled eating times can help with energy levels and boost your mood. The average recommended calorie intake is around 2,000 calories per day for women. Each woman has unique nutritional needs, but in general you need about 1-2g of protein daily for every kilogram you weigh. For a 130-lb. woman (58kg), that means taking in up to 116g of protein daily. Most people do not eat enough food just to maintain their daily nutritional needs. And, while I know it seems counterintuitive, especially if you are trying to lose weight, building muscle is important as it burns fat/calories and helps maintain normal bone health. You cannot build muscle without protein. Stress and anxiety are also big energy zappers, so to lower stress levels, try walking, listening to music, or talking to friends. It's also easy to confuse hunger and fatigue with thirst, so make sure you are drinking plenty of water.

Women's nutrition and Fitness:

Nutrition and diet are critical to overall health. Being nutritionally fit means finding the right "fuel" so you perform at your best. A good diet isn't just healthy and nutritious, it must also be sustainable. Trendy or gimmick diets can offer short-term success, but often are not sustainable. Maintaining a healthy, balanced, and sustainable diet helps build wellness across many areas of health. The right nutrition can also help you achieve optimal emotional, cognitive, and physical performance. When you eat right, you're likely to feel more energized with better focus, judgment, accuracy, and reaction time. Follow these additional nutrition tips to optimize mental performance.

Nutritional Food:

1. Vegetables leafy greens, cruciferous veggies (broccoli, cauliflower), bell peppers, carrots, mushrooms, onions, and tomatoes.
2. Fruits like berries, cherries, apples, bananas, citrus, tropical fruit (mango, pineapple), and kiwi.
3. Grains and starchy veggies like whole grains such as oats, brown rice, whole grain bread, potatoes, legumes, beans, and peas.
4. Lean proteins like poultry, fish, lean red meat, low-fat dairy, beans, nuts, seeds, and soy products.
5. Healthy fats like nuts and seeds, olive oil, and avocados. Etc...

Women's Fertility and nutrition:

Besides aging, a number of non-modifiable lifestyle-related factors such as elevated consumption of caffeine and stress, agonist sports, chronic exposure to environmental pollutants, and other nutritional habits exert a negative impact on a women's fertility. In particular, metabolic disorders including diabetes, obesity, and hyperlipidemia commonly associated to hypercaloric diets are suspected to affect a woman's fertility either by direct damage to oocyte health and differentiation, or by indirect interference with the pituitary-hypothalamic axis, resulting in dysfunctional oogenesis. Obese women show decreased insulin sensitivity determining persistent hyperinsulinemia, which may be involved in the pathogenesis of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome. Thus, the reduced insulin secretion induced by dietary adjustments is an attractive non-pharmacological treatment to prevent infertility, and a Mediterranean diet aimed at maintaining normal body mass may be effective in the preservation of ovarian health and physiology. Furthermore, in relation to the oxidative stress as a co-factor of defective oocyte maturation, an appropriate intake of proteins, antioxidants and methyl-donor supplements may decrease the bioavailability of toxic oxidants resulting in the protection of oocyte maturation. Infertility is a major problem in modern society and recurs in as much as 20–30% of the fertile female population. The American Society of Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) delineates infertility as the failure to conceive after one or more years of attempts of natural fertilization, with the World Health Organization (WHO) reporting up to 80 million women world-wide having been affected by this disease to date, with a prevalence of 50% of all women in developing countries.

Women's health and nutrition:

Healthy eating means getting nutrients primarily from food rather than from vitamins or

other supplements. Some women might need vitamins, minerals, or other supplements at certain times in life like before or during pregnancy. But most women, most of the time, should get their essential nutrients from what they eat and drink. Healthy eating is a way of eating that improves your health and helps prevent disease. It means choosing different types of healthy food from all of the food groups (fruits, vegetables, grains, dairy, and proteins), most of the time, in the correct amounts for you. Healthy eating also means not eating a lot of foods with added sugar, sodium (salt), and saturated and trans fats. Well-nourished women are better able to provide for themselves, their children, and their families. Well-nourished mothers are more likely to have infants with healthy birth weights, and such children are less likely to ever suffer from malnutrition.

Conclusion:

Thus Nutrition for women is critical because inadequate nutrition affects not only themselves but also the health of their children. Requirements for macronutrients and micronutrients are significantly increased during pregnancy to support the growth of the foetus, and the development of the placenta and maternal tissues. Women represent the cornerstone of a family's overall health, ensuring they have access to quality care also can lead to improved health for children and families. The health of families and communities are no doubt, tied to the health of women

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